

ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR SELF CONFIDENCE

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ABSTRACT

The present research was conducted to study achievement motivation of senior secondary school students in relation to their self-confidence. The sample comprised of 100 students 50 students from urban area and 50 students from rural area. The researcher had used descriptive method for collecting data and applied various statistical technique i.e. mean, standard deviation, 't'-test and correlation for analyzing the data. The result showed that there exist a significant difference between the urban and rural students of their achievement motivation and self-confidence. The study suggested that increase in achievement motivation scores leads to increase in self-confidence scores and vice-versa.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an activity or process, which transform the behaviour of a person from instinctive to human behaviour. Man instead of acting impulsively acts rationally. It is the completer development of the individuality of the child so that he can make an original contribution to human life according to the best of his capacity.

In the absence of proper motivation and guidance, man is like a boat, which flow with water waves here and there having no destination. With right direction and proper motivation, students can ride the chariots towards their success and achieve their final goals. Education plays an important role in educating and talenting the children according to their talents, personality, confidence and interest. Students set up their motives and struggle hard to attain them. Proper education system cultivates the knowledge skill, positive attitude, sense of purpose and confidence essential for building a dynamic, vibrant and cohesive nation.

Achievement motivation is relatively a new concept in the world of motivation. McClelland and Atkinson developed the concept of achievement motivation in 1957. It refers to a person's effort to master a task, achieve excellence, overcome obstacles, perform better than others and take pride in exercising talent. **According to McClelland and Atkinson, "Achievement motivation may be associated with a variety of goals, but in general, the behaviour adopted will involve the attainment of some standard of excellence."** Thus, achievement motivation is a task-oriented behaviour that allows the individual's performance to be evaluated according to some internally or externally imposed criterion, which involves the individual in competing with others or that otherwise with some standard of excellence.

Self-confidence refers to a person's perceived ability to tackle situations successfully without learning on others and to have a positive self-evaluation. A self-confident person perceives himself to be socially competent, emotionally mature, intellectually adequate, successful, satisfied, decisive, optimistic, independent, self-reliant, self-assured, forward moving, fair assertive and having leadership qualities. In the words of Basavanna (1975), "Self confidence refers to an individual's perceived ability to act effectively in a situation to overcome obstacles and to get things go all right."

OBJECTIVES

- To study the level of achievement motivation of senior secondary school students.
- To study the level of self-confidence of senior secondary school students.
- To compare the level of achievement motivation of rural and urban senior secondary school students.
- To compare the level of self-confidence of rural and urban of senior secondary school students.
- To study the relationship between achievement motivation and self-confidence of senior secondary school students.

HYPOTHESES

- There exists no significant difference between the mean scores of achievement motivation of rural and urban senior secondary school students.
- There exists no significant difference between the means scores of self-confidence of rural and urban senior secondary school students.
- There exists a significant relationship between achievement motivation and self-confidence of senior secondary school students.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

- **Methodology:** - Descriptive method of research was used in present study.
- **Tools :-** In the present study the tools used for collecting data were :-
 - DEO-MOHAN achievement motivation scale by DR. (MRS.) PRATIBHA DEO AND ASHA MOHAN.
 - REKHA GUPTA'S self-confidence inventory (ASCI).
- **Sample:** - The sample of the present study was comprised 100 Govt senior secondary school students (50 students from urban area and 50 from rural area) of Kurukshetra District. In order to keep the study manageable a random sampling procedure adopted in the study.
- **Statistical Techniques Used:** - Mean, S.D. and 't' test was employed to assess whether there exist any significant difference in the scores of various variables of the study.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Analysis and interpretation of data further researchers to attack the related problem with appropriate statistical techniques to avoid the unnecessary labour.

Testing of Hypothesis-I

Table 1.1 Significance of difference between the mean scores of achievement motivation of urban and rural senior secondary school students.

Area	No	Mean	S.D.	SE.D	“t” ratio	level of Significance
Rural	50	125.30	14.49	4.75	2.26	Significant at 0.05 level.
Urban	50	136.06	16.31			

Interpretation: -

The ‘t’ ratio (2.26) is greater than the table value of 0.05 level. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (Ho). Thus, there is a significant difference in achievement motivation of urban and rural of senior secondary school students. It means that achievement motivation scores are depending on the area. However, this result may vary from sample to sample.

Testing of Hypothesis-II

Table 1.2 Significance of difference between the mean scores of self-confidence of urban and rural senior secondary school students.

Area	No	Mean	S.D.	SED	‘t’ ratio	level of Significance
Rural	50	26.72	4.89	0.75	4.75	Significant At 0.05 level (1.98)
Urban	50	30.28	7.14			

Interpretation: - The ‘t’ ratio (4.75) is greater than the table value at 0.05 level (1.98). Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is a significant difference in the self-

confidence of urban and rural senior secondary school students i.e. self-confidence is depend on area. However, this result may vary from sample to sample.

Testing of Hypothesis-III

Table 1.3 Correlation between achievement motivation and self-confidence of urban and rural senior secondary school students.

Achievement Motivation	Self-Confidence	Level of Significance
EX=13068	EY=2850	Significant At 0.05 level (0.195)
EX ² =1734412	EY ² =85282	
	EXY=377534 N=100	

'r'=0.49 (Correlation Value)

Interpretation: -

As the calculate value of 'r' is 0.49 which is greater than the tabular value at 0.05 level of significance so we accept the hypothesis III. Thus, there exist significant relationship between achievement motivation and self-confidence of urban and rural senior secondary school student. As calculated value of 'r' is positive so there is a positive relationship between achievement motivation and self-confidence. It means that increase in achievement motivation scores leads to increase in self-confidence scores and vice versa.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

- There exists a significant difference in the means scores of achievement motivation of urban and rural senior secondary school students. It is clear from table no 1.1 we find that the mean score of achievement motivation of rural area students is 125.3 and mean score of achievement motivation of urban area students is 136.5. There exists a difference between the mean score of urban and rural students. Thus, the urban area students have slightly more achievement motivation level than rural counterpart. This means that achievement motivation score depends on area.

- There exists a significant difference in the self-confidence of urban and rural senior secondary school students. It is clear from table no 1.2 we found that the mean score of self-confidence of rural area students is 26.72 and mean score of self-confidence of urban area students is 30.28. There exists a difference between the mean scores of urban and rural students. Thus, the urban area students have slightly more self-confidence than rural counterpart. This means self-confidence is depending upon area.
- There exist significant relationship between achievement motivation and self-confidence of senior secondary school students. It is clear from table no 1.3 we find that the value of 'r' is 0.49. Therefore, there is a positive relationship between achievement motivation and self-confidence. It means that increase in achievement motivation scores leads to increase in self-confidence scores and vice-versa.

Thus, as per above interpretation and finding it has been concluded that the achievement motivation has a significant effect on the self-confidence of the students.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

In the present study, the investigator found that self-confidence and achievement motivation are correlated with each other. Self-confidence and achievement motivation are positively correlated. These results will give immense help to parents, teachers, guidance workers, counselors and they come to know the reason why their children are shy and introvert and cannot adjust themselves with others.

Teachers can play a very important role in making the child more self-confident as the child spends most of his active time with teachers. Teacher can take different measures to develop self-confidence and achievement motivation of students. The school administration should make of a point that motivation is the key to all effective learning. School should manage the institutional administration in such a way that it would provide motivational inputs to every learner.

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